

Problems of Liability in the Form of Penalty Payment

Rajabov Sherzodbek Ravshanbekovich

Independent Researcher at Tashkent State University of Law

sherzodbekrajabov@gmail.com

Annotation:

The article examines the institution of penalty (neustojka) in Roman law. Penalty (stipulatio poenae) as a conditional agreement obligated a person who breached a contract to pay a monetary sum to the injured party. The research reveals that the main purpose of penalty was to exert pressure on the debtor and ensure the main obligation. It is emphasized that the obligation to pay penalty depended on whether the debtor was liable for the breach of contract. The article demonstrates the parties' right to include penalty clauses in contracts and its significance. The analysis shows that contract breach was the main condition that triggered the penalty obligation, and penalty served as an indirect mechanism for compelling the debtor to fulfill the obligation.

Key words:

penalty, Roman law, stipulatio poenae, conditional agreement, contract breach, debtor, obligation, monetary penalty, legal security, contract law

The penalty institution occupies a distinctive place in civil law relations. Scientific debates continue regarding the formation and development of this institution, its essence and functional aspects. The legal nature of the penalty institution has a complex and multifaceted character, and in this regard, interpreting penalty as "a method of securing the performance of obligations" or as "a measure of civil liability" are among the widely accepted approaches.

In Roman law, penalty (stipulatio poenae) was understood as a conditional agreement obligating a person who breached a contract to pay a certain amount of money to the injured party. The purpose of such agreements in Roman law was to exert pressure on the debtor and secure the main obligation. Here, the obligation to pay the penalty was

contingent upon the debtor being liable for breach of contract. By including a penalty clause in the contract, the parties were able to assess as much as possible the consequences of their rights being violated at the time of contract signing. The breach of contract served as the condition triggering the penalty obligation, which was usually expressed in the form of a specific monetary amount and functioned as a mechanism compelling the debtor to perform the obligation.¹.

In the English legal system, existing research has been conducted in economic and legal directions, where one can often see the application of penalty and liquidated damages in judicial practice. Although different definitions exist in various jurisdictions, the doctrine mainly classifies as distinctive "penalties" those clauses that do not reasonably take into account expected or actual damages at the time of contract formation, or that establish damages that can be easily determined by a court. If the amount specified in the contract is excessive or insufficient, it allows courts the possibility to reduce or increase this amount. Liquidated damages may serve as exclusive or optional legal remedies for contracting parties².

Most courts limit the available legal remedies when damage clauses are optional. They provide specific enforcement rights when necessary, but do not establish the recovery of damages³.

In civil law doctrine, although there are problems in the application of "statutory penalty" and "contractual penalty," we can see that rules regarding the application of provisions such as "astreinte" and "judicial penalty" have not been established. Although norms concerning penalty exist in civil legislation, problems related to ensuring its recovery remain unresolved. In particular, issues concerning ensuring the enforcement of issued court documents and determining the monetary amount to be paid by the debtor to

¹ Карапетов А. Г. Неустойка как средство защиты прав кредитора в российском и зарубежном праве. - М. : Статут, 2006. - 286 с // Социальные и гуманитарные науки. Отечественная и зарубежная литература. Сер. 4, Государство и право: Реферативный журнал. 2007. №1. -80-6.

² Steven Walt. Penalty Clauses and Liquidated Damages. University of Virginia Law School. The John M. Olin Program in Law and Economics Working Paper Series. 2009. 57 p. <https://law.bepress.com/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?referer=&httpsredir=1&article=1184&context=uvalwps>

³ Hatzis, Aristides N. (2002). Having the Cake and Eating it Too: Efficient Penalty Clauses in Common and Civil Contract Law, 22 International Review of Law and Economics, 381- 406.; Mattei, Ugo (1995). The Comparative Law and Economics of Penalty Clauses, 43 American Journal of Comparative Law, 427-445.

the creditor in case of non-performance of debt remain on the agenda (application of astreinte, establishment of collection companies, etc.). For example, today in legal practice, although decisions are made regarding penalty recovery for non-performance of obligations, their enforcement is questionable, and the probability of non-enforcement can be said to be very high (particularly due to lack of funds, etc.).

A.Odinaev, while researching the essence of penalty, draws attention to its connection with damages and its service in preventing harm. In his opinion, "problems arising as a result of extraordinary events such as the global spread of coronavirus infection and the collapse of the 'Sardoba Water Reservoir' dam in the Sardoba district of our country, including gaps in our legislative base regarding compensation for damages suffered by farms, farmer enterprises, and cooperatives, should be noted"⁴. Additionally, the researcher indicates that the origin of penalty liability, the form of penalty recovery, and the procedure for its calculation can be established in the penalty agreement itself or by reference to a specific normative document. He shows that failure to comply with the written form of a penalty agreement results in its invalidity.

Although the author's opinion appears well-founded in this regard, there are debatable situations in some places. In particular, it can be seen that there are extremely numerous opposing views in the scholarly community regarding the adoption of referential norms. Moreover, compliance or non-compliance with the form of penalty is determined by rules established in the legal system. That is, statutory or contractual penalty naturally affects its form and content.

This is related to "astreinte" (French: astreinte), which is widespread in European Union countries and is one of the most popular methods of economic incentivization for the enforcement of court decisions. In this regard, various viewpoints have been put forward in scholarly literature for several years, and the necessity of expressing it in civil

⁴ Одинаев А.С. Неустойка қўллашга оид фуқаролик-ҳуқуқий қонунчиликни такомиллаштириш / А. С. Одинаев. — Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. — 2020. — № 22 (312). — С. 666-669. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/312/70774>.

legislation is noted⁵.

According to French law, the question arises whether *astreinte* can be "cancelled" through agreement of the parties' wills in material-legal relations. According to Article 131-4 of the French Enforcement Code, the amount of initial *astreinte* ("liquidation") is determined taking into account the conduct of the person against whom the *astreinte* was imposed and the difficulties they encountered in executing the court decision.

It is also appropriate to expand *astreinte* in terms of the scope of subjects, including creating the possibility of applying it not only to the debtor, but also to third parties who obstruct the execution of court decisions. Third parties may be persons who fall within the scope of the court executor's activities, particularly those who are safeguarding the debtor's property or paying their obligations. This serves to accelerate the execution of court decisions and increase the responsibility of third parties in conducting enforcement proceedings.

Another important issue deserves attention. Article 326 of the Civil Code contains a number of provisions that reduce the effectiveness of the penalty institution, which may create problematic situations in the practical application of this legal mechanism. The content of the studied court decisions shows that in most cases where one of the parties (the debtor) is a state enterprise or institution, or where this article is applied without any grounds, decisions are made to reduce the penalty. This situation constitutes the majority in economic court cases. In some cases, there are also instances of providing unsubstantiated explanations such as the debtor's "helplessness" or "lack of funds."⁶

The first conceptual deficiency of Article 326 of the Civil Code lies in the fact that it is expressed in a manner that allows the reduction of penalty to be interpreted not as an "exceptional case," but as a general rule. The general provision stated in the norm that "the court has the right to reduce the penalty" opens the way for interpreting penalty reduction

⁵ Кузнецов Е. Н. Астрэнт (*astreinte*) как способ принуждения должника в исполнительном производстве Франции // Российский ежегодник гражданского и арбитражного процесса. 2003. № 2. С. 430–446.

⁶ www.Public.sud.uz

as a broad discretionary power⁷ of courts. As a result, in judicial practice, penalty is viewed as a payment that can be reduced in almost any situation (for example, typically only 10 percent of the penalty is recovered), which weakens its function of securing contract performance and obligations. This undermines the principle of compliance with terms agreed upon between parties in contractual relations.

The next serious deficiency is that the criteria of the disproportionality concept expressed through the phrase "if the penalty appears disproportionate to the consequences of the creditor's breach of obligation" are not clearly defined. The vagueness of these criteria gives courts the opportunity to interpret the concept of "disproportionality" in their own way. According to the principle of legal certainty, the content of legal norms should be understood uniformly by all legal subjects. However, the vagueness of the criteria in this article leads to different decisions being made by different courts, resulting in inconsistent formation of judicial practice.

Developing explanations and recommendations for the effective application of astreinte in Uzbekistan's judicial practice is important for the judiciary's correct understanding and application of the astreinte institution. In this regard, it would be appropriate to adopt a resolution of the Plenum of the Supreme Court and provide methodological guidelines to the enforcement department, Ministry of Justice, and other interested agencies. These explanations and recommendations should cover issues such as criteria for establishing astreinte, its amount, terms, and liquidation of astreinte (determining the final amount).

The introduction of these proposals into Uzbekistan's legislation will serve to create an effective economic incentive mechanism for ensuring the execution of court decisions, strengthen guarantees for protecting citizens' rights and legitimate interests in court, enhance the authority of the judiciary, and ultimately ensure the implementation of an important principle of the rule of law – the inevitable execution of court decisions.

In our opinion, it would be appropriate to introduce the following addition to the

⁷ Discretionary powers are the right granted by law to state bodies or officials to act at their own discretion when making decisions within established limits.

Civil Code:

“Article 235¹. Protection of Creditor Rights in Obligations

In case the debtor fails to perform the obligation, the creditor has the right to demand performance of the obligation through court, unless otherwise provided by this Code, other laws, or contract, or unless it follows from the nature of the obligation. Upon the creditor's demand, the court may decide to recover a monetary sum in their favor (first part of Article 260) if the specified court document is not executed, whereby the amount is determined by the court based on the principles of fairness, proportionality, and inadmissibility of gaining profit from unlawful or unconscionable conduct. No one has the right to profit from their own unlawful or unconscionable behavior.

The creditor's protection of their rights in accordance with the first part of this article does not release the debtor from liability for non-performance or inadequate performance of the obligation (Chapter 24).”